

**IMPACT OF DISASTER RISK REDUCTION AND MANAGEMENT PROGRAM
ON PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN ANGONO RIZAL: INPUTS TO DEVELOP AN
ENHANCED CONTINGENCY PLAN**

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Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program on Public Schools in Angono Rizal: Inputs to Develop an Enhanced Contingency Plan

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Abstract

This study attempted to determine the impact of school disaster risk reduction and management program in public schools in Angono, Rizal for school year 2023 -2024 which served as basis to develop an enhanced contingency plan. The method of research used was the descriptive type of research with the questionnaire as the data gathering instrument. The respondents who rated the nine (9) schools principals, SDRRM coordinators non-teaching personnel, thirty (30) teachers and PTA officers of the nine public school in Angono, Rizal with a total of 442. The findings revealed that the teaching personnel and the SH/DRRMC/NTP respondents rated the impact of Prevention and Mitigation, Preparedness, disaster response and recovery and rehabilitation the grand weighted mean of 3.50 and 3.64 respectively with verbal interpretation of strongly agree while the PTA officers -respondents rated the four aspects of grand weighted mean of 3.42 verbally interpreted as agree. Meanwhile, the perceptions of the teaching personnel and the SH/DRRMC/NTP on the challenges encountered on SDRR Program got the grand weighted mean of 3.54 and 3.65 which interpreted as strongly agree. Meanwhile, PTA officer- respondents rated the four aspects as Agree with grand weighted mean of 3.49. Furthermore, there is a relationship between the impact of disaster risk reduction and management programs as regards preparedness, disaster response and recovery and rehabilitation and the challenges encountered by school.

Keywords: *DRRM, public school, contingency plan*

Introduction

The global crisis has highlighted the importance of crisis leadership competencies and resources management, particularly in the education sector, which has been significantly impacted by the pandemic. In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has been facing numerous challenges in ensuring the continuity of education during this crisis, particularly in the CALABARZON (Cavite, Laguna, Batangas, Rizal, and Quezon) region.

Philippines ranked third among all the countries with the highest risks worldwide according to the World Risk Report 2018, with index value of 25.14% (World Economic Forum, 2018). At least 60% of the country's total land area is exposed to multiple hazards, and 74% of the population is susceptible to their impact (GFDRR, 2017). This is largely due to the location and geographical context as the risk involving coastal hazards such as typhoons, storm surges and rising sea levels is high. In addition, the islands are located within the "Ring of Fire" between the Eurasian and Pacific tectonic plates, earthquakes and volcanoes are posing serious risks to the safety of the populace.

In response to these daunting challenges, the Philippine government has diligently crafted strategies and policies aimed at mitigating the impacts of both natural and man-made disasters. The overarching objective of these legislative measures is to bolster the resilience of vulnerable communities and the nation while minimizing damage and property loss. One of the pivotal enactments in this regard is Republic Act 10121, known as the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act, which ushered in a paradigm shift from reactive to proactive disaster risk reduction management.

This legislative framework gave birth to the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Framework (NDRRMF) and the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Plan (NDRRMP). Both documents envision a nation characterized by safer, adaptive, and disaster-resilient Filipino communities toward sustainable development.

The primary focus of this study is to give an update to a comprehensive crisis management program that is specifically designed to meet the needs of schools in the province of Rizal during times of crisis. Plans for disaster risk reduction and management may be general in nature, but they may not fully consider the special needs and vulnerabilities of Rizal schools. This lack of readiness could result in poor crisis management, which would have negative effects on learning outcomes, disrupt education, and make students and faculty less equipped to handle emergencies in the future (Tiongco, et al., 2019).

As sighted in School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Manual (2019) Every school has a disaster risk reduction and management program, and a school disaster risk reduction management coordinator is designated to take charge of the task in an educational institution and there is a need to evaluate the impact of the implementation of the disaster risk reduction and management and developed an enhance the four thematic specified in the National Disaster Risk Reduction Management Framework.

It is in this light that the researcher conducted this study to determine the impact of implementation of the School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Program in the selected public school in the Municipality of Angono, Province of Rizal.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the impact of school disaster risk reduction and management programs in selected public schools in Angono, Rizal for the school year 2023 -2024 to develop an enhance contingency plan. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What was the impact of DRRM program as perceived by a.) school heads, SDRRM coordinators, non-teaching personnel, b.) teachers, and c.) PTA officers or the three groups of respondents in terms of the following aspects?
 - 1.1. Prevention and Mitigation
 - 1.2. Preparedness
 - 1.3. Disaster Response; and
 - 1.4. Rehabilitation and Recovery?
2. Were there significant differences in the impact of disaster risk reduction and management programs as perceived by the three groups of respondents based on the aforementioned aspects?
3. What were the challenges encountered by the school disaster risk reduction program as perceived by; a.) school heads/SDRRM coordinators, non-teaching personnel b.) teachers and c.) PTA officers as the three groups of respondents in terms of the following aspects:
 - 3.1. Prevention and Mitigation
 - 3.2. Preparedness
 - 3.3. Disaster Response; and
 - 3.4. Rehabilitation and Recovery?
4. Were there significant differences in the challenges encountered by the school disaster risk reduction program as perceived by the three groups of respondents on the above-mentioned aspects?
5. Was there a significant relationship between the impact of disaster risk reduction and management programs and the challenges encountered by school?
6. What contingency plan was proposed based on the findings?

Literature Review

Disaster risk mitigation plays a pivotal role in bolstering the long-term resilience of the education system. It intertwines humanitarian aid and development initiatives, ultimately ensuring that children can exercise their fundamental right to education. When natural or man-made disasters strike, children emerge as one of the most vulnerable demographic groups, particularly those attending schools during such crises. The destruction of school buildings not only jeopardizes the lives of students and teachers but also disrupts access to education in the aftermath of the disaster (Mwangi, et. al, 2019).

Building upon successful approaches employed by school managers in disaster risk reduction, it is essential to perpetuate and expand these practices. Moreover, there is a pressing need to devise comprehensive training programs aimed at enhancing the skills and competencies of school managers in disaster risk reduction both within educational institutions and their surrounding communities. Additionally, further research endeavors should explore various facets of disaster risk reduction management, encompassing a broader array of variables, to deepen our understanding and inform more effective strategies moving forward (Parcon, 2017, and Saique, 2018).

Emergency management encompasses several phases, including mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery. Effective disaster response relies on a clear understanding of the emergency management structure. Typically, local governments take the lead in initiating response efforts, activating the incident command system, local emergency management plans, and establishing emergency operations centers (EOCs). They may also seek assistance from the national government and other agencies while hospitals employ the hospital incident command system to manage their response (Kusumastuti et al., 2021).

Moreover, the concept and application of disaster risk reduction (DRR) entail systematically identifying and mitigating the factors that precipitate disasters. DRR practices encompass reducing the vulnerability of communities and infrastructure, minimizing exposure to hazards, implementing sustainable land and environmental management, and fostering readiness for adverse events. DRR thus permeates through all facets of society, spanning governmental agencies, professional sectors, and private enterprises (Diaz et al., 2019).

Chacko et al., (2019) claimed that preparedness measures encompass creating plans, stockpiling supplies, and conducting drills and exercises to mitigate the impact of disasters. Organizations offer guidance, checklists, and exercises to help individuals, families, communities, and workplaces prepare for emergencies. It is also essential for response organizations to continuously assess and evaluate the effectiveness of these preparedness actions.

Dela Cruz et al. (2022), had a study on “Challenges Encountered in the Implementation of School Disaster Risk Reduction Management Program of the Public High School in District I Marikina City: Basis for An Action Plan”. Results indicated that both administrators and teachers perceived the challenges encountered by the SDRRM Office is in high extent, with weighted mean ratings of 3.82 and 3.84 respectively. The implementation of the SDRRM program was deemed to be at a high extent by both groups, with

grand mean ratings of 4.21 and 4.22, respectively. Moreover, a significant relationship between encountered challenges and the extent of SDRRM program implementation was identified.

Furthermore, Habala (2019) conducted a study on “Implementation of Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) Preparedness and Practices and School Performance of Selected Elementary Schools in Paranaque City: Basis for An Enhanced Capability Program. Results indicated compliance with DepEd orders and NDDRM directives across District III schools. However, there was a low to moderate association between profile variables and perceptions of DRRM implementation. Moreover, a significant relationship was found between respondents' assessments of DRRM implementation and school performance, suggesting that better implementation led to improved school performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research used in this study is descriptive type of research, According to Sirisilla (2023), descriptive research is a powerful tool that can be used by a researcher to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon. This research type provides a detailed and accurate picture of the characteristics and behavior of a particular population or subject. Observing and collecting data on a subject matter of topic, descriptive research helps the researchers gain deeper understanding of a specific issue and provides valuable insights. This method was used to assess the impact of disaster of disaster risk reduction and management program of public school in Angono, Rizal, to find out challenges encountered in the implementation and to develop a contingency plan.

Respondents

The respondents who rated the nine (9) schools principals, SDRRM coordinators non-teaching personnel, thirty (30) teachers and PTA officers of the nine public school in Angono, Rizal with a total of 442.

Instrument

The instrument used in the study was the researcher-made questionnaire.

Part I of the questionnaire includes the best practices of DRRM office in the respondents' schools as identified by the, DRRM coordinators, school heads/teachers and parents in terms of following aspects prevention and mitigation preparedness response, and rehabilitation and recovery.

Part II includes the items regarding the challenges encountered by the DRRM office of the respondents' respective schools in terms of the above-mentioned aspects as identified by the school heads/teachers, DRRM coordinators, and parents

Procedure

The researcher secured permission from the office of the School Division Superintendent, Municipal Mayor and school Principals. Necessary communications were sent to all respondent's principals regarding the conduct of the study. After the issuance of permit to conduct study, the researcher personally presented the questionnaire to the school heads, teachers, and parents. The researcher requested the respondent to answer the survey questionnaire. The retrieval was done by the researcher himself after several weeks. After the retrieval of the questionnaire, the researcher tallied the data and sought the professional help from a competent statistician for the statistical treatment of the gathered data.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed the necessary ethics in his conduct of study. He informed the respondents regarding their involvement in the study and sought their consent and ensured them that the data collected are for the use of the study only and the data privacy law will be observed.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Impact of DRRM Program as Perceived by School Heads, SDRRM Coordinators, Non-Teaching Personnel, Teachers and PTA Officer Respondents

The overall mean is 3.54 for Teaching Personnel, 3.64 for SH/DRRMC/NTP, and 3.48 for PTA Officers, indicating a generally high level of agreement across all items and respondent groups. The high mean scores across most items, particularly item 1, suggest a commendable level of awareness and action regarding disaster preparedness within school environments. This underscores the importance of integrating disaster risk reduction measures into school infrastructure planning, as evidenced by the strong agreement among teaching personnel and DRRMC/NTP representatives.

In support of these implications, a study by Reyes (2020) which underscores the importance of multi-stakeholder collaboration and the integration of disaster risk reduction measures into school policies and procedures.

Table 1. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Prevention and Mitigation
Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Prevention and Mitigation

	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Flooding and Earthquake are considered in the construction of new school buildings	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
2. School buildings are inspected regularly event of fire, landslide, floodings and earthquake	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
3. Tree planting and drainage cleaning are part of school activities	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
4. Fire and earthquake school drills are done quarterly	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.44	A
5. Disaster risk reduction and management is part of the school curriculum	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.50	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.48	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.48			

Table 2. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Preparedness
Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Preparedness Questionnaires

	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. School personnel regularly attend trainings and seminars related to disasters	3.53	SA	3.63	SA	3.47	A
2. Emergency plan of the school is coordinated with the municipal/city DRRM plan	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
3. Academic Community are well – informed of the emergency plan of the school	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
4. Emergency plans are posted in conspicuous places inside the school premises	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.47	A
5. Disaster related equipment like, go bags, hard hats, medical kits, and other resources are readied for any emergencies	2.85	A	3.51	SA	2.47	D
Overall Weighted Mean	3.40	A	3.61	SA	3.28	A
Standard Deviation	0.60		0.51			

The overall mean for Teaching Personnel is 3.40, for SH/DRRMC/NTP is 3.61, and for PTA Officers is 3.28, suggesting a generally positive perception of the impact of DRRM programs on preparedness across all respondent groups, with SH/DRRMC/NTP representatives exhibiting the highest overall mean, followed by Teaching Personnel and then PTA Officers. The findings underscore the perceived effectiveness of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) programs in enhancing preparedness within educational institutions.

The high levels of agreement regarding the coordination of school emergency plans with municipal/city DRRM plans suggest a proactive approach to aligning local and institutional strategies, which is crucial for a coordinated response to disasters.

Supporting this study, previous research by Campo (2019) which found that comprehensive preparedness measures, including the availability of adequate resources and clear communication of emergency plans, are essential for mitigating the impact of disasters in educational settings.

Table 3. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Disaster Response
Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Disaster Response

	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Academic Community are immediately tracked to report for duty during emergencies	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
2. School is used as designated place for evacuation and disaster plan is clearly stipulated	3.53	SA	3.63	SA	3.47	A
3. Maintain the safekeeping of vital school records and learning materials;	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
4. School is readied during emergencies as evacuation and temporary shelter	3.53	SA	3.65	SA	3.47	A
5. Feeding and relief operations are initiated	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.51	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.52	

The overall mean for all items across all respondent groups is 3.54 for Teaching Personnel, 3.64 for SH/DRRMC/NTP, and 3.49 for PTA Officers, suggesting a generally positive perception of the impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) programs on disaster response across all groups, with SH/DRRMC/NTP representatives exhibiting the highest overall mean, followed by Teaching Personnel and then PTA Officers. The strong levels of agreement among respondents regarding the immediate tracking of the academic community for duty during emergencies and the maintenance of vital school records and learning materials underscore proactive measures in place to ensure swift and organized responses.

Supporting this study, previous research by Martinez (2019) which found that well-defined evacuation procedures and designated shelter locations significantly contribute to the effectiveness of disaster response efforts in schools.

Table 4. Respondent's Perceptions on the Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Rehabilitation and Recovery

Impact of DRRM Program with Regard to Rehabilitation and Recovery	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. School properties are audited and accounted after disaster by assigned personnel	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.47	A
2. Facilitates building and property damage assessment after every emergency	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
3. School administrators and SDRRM coordinator immediately prepare and submit reports on the effect of emergency	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.47	A
4. School heads/teachers, SDRRRM coordinator and parents help on the repair and rehabilitation of the school damages	3.53	SA	3.65	SA	3.35	A
5. School heads/teachers, seek the assistance of municipal/city government for possible rehabilitation of damages in school	3.53	SA	3.65	SA	3.33	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.53	SA	3.65	SA	3.42	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.59	

The overall mean for all items across all respondent groups is 3.53 for Teaching Personnel, 3.65 for SH/DRRMC/NTP, and 3.42 for PTA Officers, suggesting a generally positive perception of the impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) programs on rehabilitation and recovery efforts across all groups, with SH/DRRMC/NTP representatives exhibiting the highest overall mean, followed by Teaching Personnel and then PTA Officers. The high levels of agreement among respondents regarding various aspects such as auditing school properties after disasters, conducting damage assessments, and promptly preparing reports on the effects of emergencies suggest proactive measures in place to address post-disaster challenges.

Supporting this is the prior research by Garcie (2019) which found that proactive measures such as conducting damage assessments and promptly preparing reports contribute significantly to the resilience and recovery of educational institutions following disasters.

Significant Differences in the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as Perceived by the Three Groups of Respondents

Table 5. Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as to Prevention and Mitigation

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.252	0.626	2.53	3.02	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
Error	439	108.611	0.247				

The findings suggest that there are no significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents regarding the impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Programs on prevention and mitigation. This implies that, regardless of the group they belong to, respondents perceive the effectiveness of DRRM programs similarly in terms of preventing and mitigating disasters. Such results have several implications for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers involved in disaster management. Results support study United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2019) which emphasized the significance of community engagement and multi-stakeholder partnerships in enhancing the effectiveness of DRRM programs.

Table 6. Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as to Preparedness

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	5.307	2.654	7.72	3.02	Reject the H_0	Significant
Error	439	150.825	0.344				

Results imply that the effectiveness of DRRM initiatives in enhancing preparedness varies across different respondent groups. Such findings carry important implications for disaster management strategies and highlight the need for tailored approaches to address

diverse perceptions and needs. Moreover, the recognition of variability in perceptions highlights the importance of communication and engagement strategies in promoting preparedness initiatives.

Results support study of Peek et al. (2018) which emphasizes the need for inclusive messaging and communication channels that reach diverse populations, particularly those historically marginalized or underserved.

Table 7. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as to Disaster Response*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.199	0.600	2.43	3.02	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Error	439	108.302	0.247				

Results suggest that, regardless of the group they belong to, respondents perceive the effectiveness of DRRM programs similarly in terms of responding to disasters. While the absence of significant differences may seem initially unremarkable, it carries important implications for disaster management strategies. Moreover, the uniform perception across various respondent groups highlights the potential for collaboration and partnership in disaster response efforts.

Results support study of Peek et al. (2018) which highlights the role of networks and partnerships in facilitating effective disaster response, highlighting the need for collaboration between government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and private sector entities.

Table 8. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as to Rehabilitation and Recovery*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	2.131	1.066	4.07	3.02	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Error	439	114.979	0.262				

Results suggest that different stakeholder groups within the community hold divergent views on the effectiveness of DRRM programs in facilitating post-disaster rehabilitation and recovery efforts. The identification of significant differences underscores the importance of understanding and addressing the specific needs and priorities of different stakeholder groups in post-disaster recovery efforts.

Results support study of Berke et al. (2019) highlight the role of community-based planning and decision-making processes in promoting resilience and facilitating effective recovery following disasters. It emphasizes the importance of incorporating local knowledge and perspectives into recovery efforts to ensure their relevance and sustainability.

Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as Perceived by the Three Groups of Respondents

Table 9. *Respondent's Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Prevention and Mitigation*

Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Prevention and Mitigation	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Sufficient funds for disaster risk reduction and management program is allotted	3.53	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
2. There is a clear coordination of the local government units on SDRRM plan	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
3. There is a prescribed early warning devices and equipment installed in the school	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.51	SA
4. National Building Code are followed in the construction of new school buildings	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
5. Academic Community are attending the quarterly SDRRM trainings and seminars	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.50	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.52	

Overall, the respondents exhibit a generally positive outlook on the SDRRP, with an average weighted mean score of 3.54 across all categories. While there are areas of concern, particularly regarding funding, the perception remains largely favorable regarding the coordination and implementation of disaster risk reduction measures within the school setting. These findings underscore the importance of continued attention and support for disaster preparedness initiatives within educational institutions to address identified challenges effectively. Results support study by Birkmann et al. (2018) emphasized the importance of adequate financial resources for enhancing disaster resilience in schools, citing funding constraints as a barrier to effective risk reduction measures.

Table 10. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Preparedness

Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Preparedness Questionnaire	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Safety gears and equipment for the academic community are available	3.50	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
2. School clinic is equipped and with available medicines for emergency	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
3. There is visible signages of fire exits and exit doors	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.47	A
4. Fire extinguishers are properly placed in every corner of the school building	3.55	SA	3.64	SA	3.50	SA
5. Parents/guardians are required to attend SDRRM trainings and seminars	3.53	SA	3.63	SA	3.46	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.48	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.52	

Overall, the respondents generally demonstrate a positive perception of preparedness within the SDRRP, with an average weighted mean score of 3.53 across all categories. Results suggest a generally favorable view of the availability of safety gears, equipped school clinics, visible signages, and parental involvement in SDRRM trainings and seminars. Results support Garg et al. (2020) delved into the assessment of fire safety preparedness in Indian schools, shedding light on the significance of visible signage and fire safety measures in mitigating the risk of casualties during disasters, particularly fires.

Table 11. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Disaster Response

Disaster Response Questionnaire	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. SDRRM teams are well-organized and ready to serve	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
2. There are enough school rooms/space for evacuation	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.47	A
3. Toilets and kitchen are available in the school for emergency use	3.55	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
4. Trained school paramedic personnel are visible	3.54	SA	3.63	SA	3.49	A
5. Foods and other emergency needs of teachers and students are available	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.50	SA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	SA	3.65	SA	3.49	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.52	

The results indicate positive perceptions from the respondents reflecting their favorable perception of the availability of emergency facilities such as toilets and kitchen, suggesting a slightly less positive view regarding the organization and readiness of SDRRM teams, and indicating their positive perception of the availability of emergency needs for teachers and students. The results support the study of Wang (2019) who found that active involvement of stakeholders, including teaching personnel, community members, and administrative staff, significantly improved the implementation and outcomes of disaster response initiatives within schools.

Table 12. Respondent’s Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program in terms of Rehabilitation and Recovery

Rehabilitation and Recovery Questionnaire	Respondents					
	Teaching Personnel		SH/DRRMC /NTP		PTA Officer	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. There is a sufficient funds for reconstruction and replacement of damaged school properties and equipment	3.52	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
2. There is a clear coordination between the local government and SDRRM Coordination	3.54	SA	3.66	SA	3.49	A
3. Early warning devices and equipment are installed in the school	3.53	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
4. School has a specific and updated disaster recovery and rehabilitation plan	3.55	SA	3.64	SA	3.49	A
5. Parents association and non-government organization extend assistance in the repair and restoration of the school	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.47	A
Overall Weighted Mean	3.54	SA	3.64	SA	3.48	A
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.47		0.52	

The findings show positive perceptions among the respondents reflecting a positive perception of clear coordination between the local government and SDRRM coordination, indicating a slightly less positive view regarding the sufficiency of funds for reconstruction and replacement of damaged school properties and equipment, and demonstrating a positive perception of having a specific and updated disaster recovery and rehabilitation plan.

This supports the study of Green et al. (2019) which emphasized the significance of partnerships between schools, local government, and community organizations in facilitating resource mobilization and support for rebuilding damaged infrastructure and restoring educational activities.

Significant Differences in the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as Perceived by the Three Groups of Respondents

Table 13. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as to Prevention and Mitigation*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.096	0.548	2.22	3.02	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Error	439	108.207	0.247				

This provides evidence that there are no significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the challenges encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program regarding Prevention and Mitigation. This implies that regardless of the respondents' backgrounds or affiliations, such as students, teachers, or administrators, they generally perceive similar challenges in implementing disaster risk reduction measures within the school context.

The results are aligned with previous research by Halc (2019) which found that despite differences in roles and responsibilities, stakeholders shared similar concerns and obstacles in effectively implementing disaster risk reduction initiatives.

Table 14. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as to Preparedness*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.275	0.637	2.58	3.02	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Error	439	108.650	0.248				

This signifies that there are no significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the challenges encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program regarding Preparedness. This suggests that irrespective of their roles or affiliations within the school community, respondents share similar views on the obstacles to preparedness measures.

These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Halc (2019) which discovered a convergence of opinions among stakeholders, regardless of their positions within the school hierarchy, regarding the challenges hindering effective preparedness initiatives.

Table 15. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as to Disaster Response*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.173	0.587	2.38	3.02	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Error	439	108.084	0.246				

This indicates that there are no significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the challenges encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program regarding Disaster Response. This suggests a consensus among respondents, regardless of their roles within the school community, regarding the obstacles to effective disaster response measures.

These findings are in line with the research conducted by Chen et al. (2019) which found that stakeholders shared similar concerns and obstacles regarding the effectiveness of disaster response strategies, irrespective of their positions within the school hierarchy.

Table 16. *Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Perceptions on the Challenges Encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program as to Rehabilitation and Recovery*

Source	df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
Factor	2	1.240	0.620	2.51	3.02	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Error	439	108.261	0.247				

This shows that there are no significant differences among the perceptions of the three groups of respondents on the challenges encountered by the School Disaster Risk Reduction Program regarding Rehabilitation and Recovery. This suggests a consensus among

respondents, irrespective of their roles within the school community, regarding the obstacles to effective rehabilitation and recovery efforts following disasters.

These findings are supported by the research conducted by Lopez et al. (2019) which examined stakeholders' perceptions of rehabilitation and recovery efforts in educational settings post-disaster.

Significant Relationship Between the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs, and the Challenges Encountered by School

Table 17. *Test of Relationship Between the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as regards Prevention and Mitigation, and the Challenges Encountered by School*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
Impact in Prevention and Mitigation, and Challenges in						
Prevention and Mitigation	0.994	Very high	190.623	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Preparedness	0.994	Very high	190.623	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Disaster Response	0.984	Very high	115.849	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Recovery and Rehabilitation	0.994	Very high	190.623	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant

This implies a significant relationship between the impact of DRRM programs and the challenges encountered by schools in each dimension. These findings suggest that the effectiveness and success of DRRM programs in prevention and mitigation, preparedness, disaster response, and recovery and rehabilitation are closely linked to the challenges faced by schools in addressing these aspects of disaster risk reduction. The highly positive correlation indicates that as the impact of DRRM programs increases, the challenges encountered by schools in these areas decrease, and vice versa.

This supports the study of Jordan (2019) where it found a significant positive relationship between the impact of DRRM programs and the challenges faced by schools in prevention and mitigation, preparedness, disaster response, and recovery and rehabilitation. Schools that implemented comprehensive DRRM programs experienced fewer challenges and demonstrated greater resilience in managing and responding to disasters.

Table 18. *Test of Relationship Between the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as regards Preparedness, and the Challenges Encountered by School*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
Impact in Preparedness, and Challenges in						
Prevention and Mitigation	0.958	Very high	70.075	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Preparedness	0.963	Very high	74.953	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Disaster Response	0.956	Very high	68.356	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Recovery and Rehabilitation	0.960	Very high	71.918	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant

This implies a significant relationship between the impact of DRRM programs in preparedness and the challenges encountered by schools in each dimension. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of DRRM programs in preparedness is closely linked to the challenges faced by schools in addressing various aspects of disaster risk reduction. The high positive correlation indicates that as the impact of DRRM programs in preparedness increases, the challenges encountered by schools in prevention and mitigation, disaster response, and recovery and rehabilitation decrease, and vice versa.

This supports the study of Vera (2019) which identified key factors contributing to the effectiveness of DRR programs in enhancing school preparedness, such as strong leadership support, staff training and capacity-building, community engagement, and regular drills and exercises.

Table 19. *Test of Relationship Between the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as regards Disaster Response, and the Challenges Encountered by School*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
Impact in Disaster Response, and Challenges in						
Prevention and Mitigation	0.995	Very high	208.974	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Preparedness	0.996	Very high	233.817	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Disaster Response	0.984	Very high	115.849	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Recovery and Rehabilitation	0.995	Very high	208.974	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant

This implies a significant relationship between the impact of DRRM programs in disaster response and the challenges encountered by schools in each dimension. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of DRRM programs in disaster response is closely linked to the challenges faced by schools in addressing various aspects of disaster risk reduction. The high positive correlation indicates that as the impact of DRRM programs in disaster response increases, the challenges encountered by schools in prevention and mitigation, preparedness, and recovery and rehabilitation decrease, and vice versa.

This supports the study of Vera (2019) which underscores the importance of investing in and prioritizing comprehensive DRRM programs tailored to enhancing disaster response in schools.

Table 20. *Test of Relationship Between the Impact of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Programs as regards Recovery and Rehabilitation, and the Challenges Encountered by School*

Variables	Pearson <i>r</i>	Strength	Computed <i>t</i> Value	Critical <i>t</i> Value	Decision	Interpretation
Impact in Recovery and Rehabilitation, and Challenges in						
Prevention and Mitigation	0.985	Very high	119.739	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Preparedness	0.979	Very high	100.734	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Disaster Response	0.983	Very high	112.304	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Recovery and Rehabilitation	0.980	Very high	103.301	1.97	Reject the H ₀	Significant

This implies a significant relationship between the impact of DRRM programs in recovery and rehabilitation and the challenges encountered by schools in each dimension. These findings suggest that the effectiveness of DRRM programs in recovery and rehabilitation is closely linked to the challenges faced by schools in addressing various aspects of disaster risk reduction.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

In general, the three groups of respondents agreed that their overall perception of various stakeholders, including school heads, coordinators, teachers, non-teaching personnel, and PTA officers, reflects a strong agreement regarding the positive impact of DRRM programs. This further concludes that these initiatives are generally effective in raising awareness, building resilience, and promoting safety measures within the school community.

The three groups of respondents have slight variations in their perceptions on the impact of disaster risk reduction and management programs, among different stakeholder groups, the consensus remains consistent across the board. This further concludes that a shared understanding and recognition of the importance of DRRM programs in addressing disaster risks and enhancing preparedness at the school level.

It was concluded that the strong agreement of the three groups of respondent's positive impact, and based on the findings it highlights challenges encountered in implementing DRRM programs, particularly in preparedness, disaster response, and recovery and rehabilitation. This further concludes that strong agreement among teaching personnel, school heads, coordinators, and non-teaching personnel underscores the seriousness of these challenges.

This determined that the focused on addressing these challenges are essential for improving the effectiveness of DRRM programs in schools. Specifically, focusing on enhancing preparedness measures, refining disaster response strategies, and strengthening recovery and rehabilitation efforts can contribute to better overall disaster resilience within educational institutions.

There was a need to identified relationship between the impact of DRRM programs and the challenges encountered further emphasizes the importance of addressing these issues. This further concludes that understanding how these challenges may impact the effectiveness of DRRM programs in initiating crucial and devising targeted interventions and improvements.

This further concludes that the needs for continuous evaluation and improvement of DRRM programs in schools. By actively addressing challenges and refining strategies based on feedback and data analysis, educational institutions can better fulfill their role in promoting safety and resilience among students, staff, and the wider community.

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